

“Role of Nanobioceramics in Enhancing Wound Healing: An Efficient and Economical Perspective”

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Abstract

Wound healing is a sophisticated process for which various treatment methods have been developed. Bioceramics with the ability to release inorganic ions in biological environments play a crucial role in cellular metabolism and exhibit bactericidal activity, contributing to numerous physiological processes. Their multifaceted roles in biological systems highlight their significance. The release of different metallic ions from bioceramics enables the repair of both hard and soft tissues. These ions may be effective in cell motility, proliferation, differentiation, adhesion, angiogenesis, and antibiosis. Unlike conventional medications, the bioactivity and antibacterial properties of bioceramics are typically not associated with side effects or bacterial resistance. Because of their remarkable mechanical qualities, bioceramics are widely known for their ability to aid in the repair of hard tissues. The application of three main types of bioceramics—oxide ceramics, silicate-based ceramics, and calcium-phosphate ceramics—in the context of wound care is covered in this review after we first examine wound treatment and its common techniques. This review presents bioceramics as an economical and effective substitute for wound healing. Our goal is to motivate scientists to use bioceramics in conjunction with other biomaterials to promote faster, safer, more cost-effective wound healing.

Key Word

Angiogenesis, Antibacterial , Wound Treatment, Bioceramic.

Introduction

The skin serves as the body's first line of defense and is essential for shielding human tissues and organs from external assaults including burns, scalds, and cuts^[1]. The epidermis, dermis, and subcutaneous tissues make up the skin. When wounds penetrate the dermis or subcutaneous tissue, the skin's ability to regenerate is diminished, and the wound heals slowly and may develop

into a chronic wound or heal by scar repair ^{[1][2]}. Wound healing is a complicated process that requires coordinated interactions between various biological systems, including the immune system, to restore the skin's anatomical and functional integrity^[3]. Hemostasis, inflammation, proliferation, and remodeling (or maturation) are the four primary phases of wound healing, during which intricate and well-coordinated interactions between several biological systems take place to restore the skin's normal structure and function ^[4]. Prolonged wound healing raises the risk of infection and, in extreme cases, may even endanger the patient's life by causing chronic diseases. Severe skin injuries can be treated with a variety of techniques, such as wound dressings, stem cell/cell therapy, platelet therapy, instrumental-based therapy, and skin transplantation. Wound dressings are frequently used because they are effective and simple to apply, yet they might not be enough to get the best possible therapeutic results. The development of innovative wound dressings that can load and release growth factors, medications, and various ions to promote accelerated healing or induce antibacterial activity is currently underway to address this challenge ^{[5], [6], [7]}. Wound dressings as carriers in direct contact with the wound site can play an important role in the targeted delivery of therapeutics. In an effort to improve overall wound healing results, numerous researchers have included growth factors and medications into wound dressings to encourage tissue regeneration. However, the short half-life, denaturation susceptibility, and high cost of growth factors are significant obstacles to their utilization ^[8]. On the other hand, a lot of medications cause adverse consequences in people. For example, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medications, which effectively reduce pain and inflammation, may impede the natural healing process of wounds by inhibiting the proliferation of skin cells and blood vessels. Additionally, steroid medications like dexamethasone have immunosuppressive and anti-inflammatory qualities, but using them can postpone wound healing ^[9]. A workable, affordable substitute is desperately needed given the problems and restrictions related to the usage of growth hormones and medications. Among bioactive materials, bioceramics with the ability to release essential ions have high therapeutic potential and at the same time create minimal side effects. Bioceramics are crystalline or amorphous ceramic materials intended for use in organ replacement or tissue repair within the human body. Since calcium (Ca) sulfate was first used for bone repair in 975 AD, these materials have reportedly been used for medical purposes ^[10]. Bioceramics are mainly recognized for their use in hard tissue replacement and repair; soft tissue regeneration applications are less commonly researched. However, bioceramics are materials with a significant potential for soft tissue regeneration due to their good cytocompatibility, release of different ions, biochemical management of the milieu, and facilitation of intercellular signaling ^[11].

2 Wound infection:-

2.1 Types of wound

Wounds are typically categorized based on how long they take to heal and how they are healed. Acute and chronic wounds are the two types^[12]. Wounds brought on by caustic substances, Acute wounds include heat, mechanical damage, electrical shock, and radioactivity; they typically Heal

in a reasonable amount of time with the right wound care. On the other hand, chronic wounds are linked to certain illnesses, including diabetes mellitus, and they don't follow the regular sequence of steps and time frame that define the typical wound-healing process. Chronic wounds often last a long time in the inflammatory stage, and this length of time is linked to with elements including the wound site's moisture balance, necrotic tissue, and bacterial burden. Furthermore, unless the underlying cause of the illness is treated, there is a very significant chance that chronic wounds may recur ^[13]. In actuality, persistent wounds may take years to heal or never heal at all. Resolving the stage and eliminating such inhibitory forces are therefore crucial. Additionally, wounds can be divided into three categories based on their depth: (1) superficial wounds, which have lost a portion of the epidermis; (2) partial-thickness wounds, which have both the epidermis and deeper dermal layers; are impacted; (3) full-thickness lesions that rupture deeper tissue and subcutaneous fat ^[14].

2.2 Normal wound healing process

Numerous cells, mediators, growth factors, and extracellular matrix (ECM) components are all involved in the intricate but precisely coordinated physiological process of wound healing. Hemostasis, inflammation, proliferation, and remodeling are all stages of the wound-healing cycle that typically occur simultaneously but overlap ^[15]. A fibrin clot forms at the site of damage during the hemostasis phase to stop blood loss and limit microbial contamination by vasoconstriction ^[16]. The inflammatory phase then starts very shortly after. The neutrophils in this process consume the bacterial cells that are already present in the wound. and release antimicrobial peptides and protease to cleanse the wound. In order to eliminate apoptotic neutrophils, which release cytokines and various growth factors for a continuous wound-healing process, the monocytes also differentiate into macrophages. After skin damage, this stage typically takes two to five days to finish ^[12]. Cell migration and proliferation make up the third phase, often known as the proliferative phase, which usually happens five days to three weeks following injury. In order to create ECM components (such as fibronectin, hyaluronic acid, collagen, and proteoglycan), fibroblasts move to the wound site during this phase. Additionally, for re-epithelization and new blood vessels ^[16] In order to provide the repaired skin more tensile strength, collagen I, which has a more organized lattice structure, eventually replaces collagen III from the freshly created extracellular matrix throughout the remodeling phase. All of the processes that were initiated upon the damage are then stopped during this period, which can last anywhere from three weeks to two years (and occasionally longer).

2.3 Wound Dressing

Protecting the wound from outside contamination is the primary goal of wound dressing. Additionally, it keeps the wound hydrated to promote healing and shield the wound's origin ^[17]. As a result, materials used to dress wounds should be affordable, hypoallergenic, biocompatible, and semi-permeable to oxygen and water. Therefore, wound dressing necessitates technological cutting-edge dressing materials as opposed to conventional wound-dressing materials like cotton and wool. In addition to maintaining the wound environment, the novel materials can transfer active chemicals to promote wound healing ^[18]. In this sense, a variety of wound-care products, including hydrogels, antibacterial agents, ointments, and creams are currently accessible and mostly made of biodegradable components in combination with polymers. such as cellulose, gelatin, collagen,

silicon, hyaluronic acid, and chitosan ^[19-23]. Because they can stop bacterial growth, quinolones ^[24], tetracyclines ^[25], cephalosporins ^[26], neomycin ^[27], and polymyxin B ^[27] are the most often used antibiotics in wound dressings. In order to prevent such resistance, treatments utilizing non-antibiotic materials, alternative antibiotics, and a combination of antibiotics with non-antibiotic materials like honey, essential oils, and nanoparticles (like Ag and Au) have been suggested for use in wound dressings ^[28].

Wound Treatment:-

Wear, cuts, burns, illnesses, mishaps, and operations can all result in wounds that destroy the skin tissue's inherent anatomical relationships.^[29]The four primary stages of the complex, dynamic, and multifaceted wound healing process are homeostasis, inflammation, proliferation, and tissue remodeling/maturation. These phases occur one after the other, with some overlap ^[30].Coagulation factors like fibronectin are released when platelets and inflammatory cells migrate to the wound site. Concurrently, a blood clot forms, forming a transient barrier. Additionally, this step causes vascular contraction, which helps stop blood loss and gets the site ready for later stages of healing ^[31, 32].The inflammatory reaction starts as soon as the hemostasis phase is finished. During this crucial phase, dead cells, germs, and foreign objects are actively removed from the wound site. The main goal is to reduce the chance of infection, which is known to hinder the healing of wounds. The inflammatory stage creates a favorable environment for later stages of wound healing by effectively removing possible sources of infection, promoting an ideal and prompt recovery. Inflammatory cells in the circulation are responsible for this process ^[33, 34]. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) are released by inflammatory cells throughout the inflammatory stage, and eventually tissue debris and bacteria are removed by neutrophils and macrophages. A number of complex processes take place during the third stage of wound healing, called proliferation. Granulation tissue creation, neovascularization (the formation of new blood vessels), fibrogenesis (the synthesis of fibrous tissue), wound contraction, and re-epithelialization (the restoration of the epithelial layer) are some of these. A vital step toward full recovery, this dynamic phase actively supports the structural and functional regeneration of the injured tissue. Through epithelialization, new granulation tissue and extracellular matrix (ECM) are created; this process lasts until the lesion heals. The primary activity during this phase is fibroblast proliferation ^[35, 36]. Even though the wound is not entirely healed by the end of the proliferation phase, the wound surface is shielded from the invasion of foreign germs and viruses by covering the defect areas with the epidermal layer.

Remodeling and maturation is the fourth and last phase of wound healing. The previously temporarily healed wound region goes through a methodical metamorphosis during this phase, being replaced with tissue that closely mimics the original. Type I collagen replaces type III collagen during a particular biochemical transformation that takes place during wound healing. This substitution contributes to the resilience and structural integrity of the newly produced tissue by increasing its tensile strength ^[37,38] (see Fig. 1). Its significance is highlighted by the crucial selection of an appropriate technique for wound therapy. The use of dressings is one of the most popular and accessible techniques. Wound dressings typically serve as a crucial physical barrier, strategically positioned to form a barrier between the wound and the outside world. By controlling moisture, temperature, and other crucial elements, these dressings actively help to maintain an ideal healing environment in addition to protecting the wound from possible pollutants (Fig. 2). This speeds up the healing of wounds and helps stop further harm or infection.

Currently, depending on the type of wound, there are different types of dressings available, including dry dressings (for example, gauze, bandage or cotton wool ^[39], transparent dressings ^[40], hydrocolloids ^[41], hydrogels ^[42], foams ^[43] and nanofibers ^[44].

In general, an ideal bandage should have a number of fundamental characteristics, such as promoting hemostasis, relieving pain, having enough mechanical qualities and flexibility, and being able to keep wounds moist ^[45-50]. Taking into account the microbes that cause problems An optimal dressing should be effective in preventing infection and preventing the development of bacterial biofilms in addition to having antibacterial action. By actively preventing microbial colonization and fostering a sterile milieu within the wound site, this dual functionality is essential for establishing an environment that promotes ideal healing circumstances. Fig. 3 illustrates the effectiveness of antibacterial dressing by showing how agents like medications and bioceramic nanoparticles can be incorporated to efficiently penetrate microorganisms and prevent wound infection.

Bacterial resistance may arise as a result of improper and excessive usage of antibiotic drugs; ceramic-based antibacterial nanoparticles are better in this regard. By interfering with their natural metabolism or directly damaging the bacterial cell membrane, these nanoparticles either kill or stop the growth of bacteria and fungi. ^[51,52]

Fig no. 1 Four consecutive and overlapping phases of wound healing.

Fig. 2. Illustrates how wound dressing functions as a protective shield, separating the injured tissue from the ambient surroundings.

Fig. 3. Covering the wound surface with antibacterial agent-loaded dressings prevents the penetration of microorganisms and wound infection.

The wound healing process is significantly influenced by a number of key ionic elements, such as calcium (Ca), phosphorus (P), zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), silver (Ag), magnesium (Mg), titanium (Ti), strontium (Sr), zirconium (Zr), silicon (Si), and aluminum (Al). The efficacy of bioceramics in soft tissue restoration has been investigated in addition to hard tissue repair^[53]. Inorganic/metallic ions naturally regulate enzyme activity and the epidermal barrier, preserve redox equilibrium, and aid in skin remodeling^[54]. In addition to stimulating angiogenesis and skin appendage regeneration, the inorganic/metallic ions released by bioceramics can also initiate antibacterial and anticancer actions (Fig. 4)

3. Cost-Effectiveness of using nanobioceramics

TABLE NO 1

Roles of metallic ions in the wound tissue regeneration and healing process.

ION	Role in the Tissue Regeneration and Healing Process	Ref.
Ca ²⁺	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Generation of thrombin and coagulation - Chemokine effects - Fibroblasts adhesion and proliferation - Keratinocytes differentiation - Controlling the activity of genes associated with angiogenesis 	[55,56]
Mg ²⁺	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Fibroblast cells' migration, adhesion, proliferation and differentiation - Collagen formation - Angiogenesis - Regulation of the inflammatory process 	[57,58]
Zn ²⁺	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - An important ion in coagulation process - Cellular immune regulation - Epithelial regeneration - ECM synthesis - Antimicrobial activity 	[57,58]
Sr ²⁺	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stimulation of pro-angiogenic growth factors secretion - hair follicle regeneration 	[59,60]
Si ⁴⁺	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stimulation of pro-angiogenic growth factors secretion - Synthesis of collagen - Glycosaminoglycans synthesis - Improvement of endothelial cells viability 	[61,62]
Cu ²⁺	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Involvement in vessel formation and angiogenesis - Inducing VEGF expression and angiogenesis - Antibacterial activity <p>Improvement of keratinocytes adhesion via induction of integrins expression</p>	[63]
Ag ⁺	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Significant antibacterial activity 	[64,65]
Au ³⁺	Anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial properties	[66,67]
Zr ⁴⁺	Antibacterial, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity	[68,69]

Fig. 4. Schematic illustration of ion-mediated functionalities in skin tissue repair.

One important issue that determines whether or not bioactive compounds, such as bioceramics, growth factors, or active pharmaceutical ingredients for wound treatment, can be mass-produced is their cost. Raw materials, labor, equipment, and human resources can all be included in the cost of manufacturing; taxes and insurance payments are not included. Growth factors and the majority of effective medicinal drugs are typically more expensive to make than bioceramics with comparatively inexpensive precursors since they are organic chemicals that require extremely complicated extraction and purification procedures. For example, it has been claimed that the cost per gram of certain growth hormones can reach 400,000 USD^[70].

4. Nanobioceramics in wound healing

Nanobioceramics are a broad class of nanoceramics used in biomedical applications and regenerative medicine due to their exceptional biocompatibility and effective interaction with live tissues. Nanobioceramics generally fall into three categories: bioinert, resorbable, and bioactive. Because of their superior mechanical properties, bioceramics are mostly used to replace or repair hard tissues. Nevertheless, inorganic ions from bioceramics can also affect macrophage polarization and activate soft tissue cells such as fibroblasts, endothelial cells, and epithelial cells. This has led to the concept of employing nanobioceramics for soft tissue regeneration^[71]. Moreover, many bioceramic nanoparticles have strong antibacterial properties, and unlike drugs, their efficacy is unaffected by bacterial resistance^[72,73].

This study investigates the use of three fundamental types of bioceramics in wound healing: oxide ceramics, silicate-based ceramics, and calcium-phosphate ceramics (Fig. 5). These compounds are frequently used to dressings to stimulate cells and provide angiogenic and antimicrobial effects. The effectiveness of these materials depends on key characteristics, such as surface activation, zeta potential, dispersion index, dimensions and architecture (smaller particles showing increased

biological activity). Numerous characteristics of bioceramic particles, including their porosity, chemical structure, heterogeneity, and hydrolytic stability, have a significant impact on both their overall performance and biological behavior. Together, these characteristics support bioceramics' biocompatibility and efficacy in a variety of applications, from tissue engineering to medical implants^[74].

Fig. 5. Three main categories of bioceramics and common inorganic ions in their structure

4.1. Oxide ceramics

Oxide ceramics are compounds made of metallic and metalloid elements, such as Al, Zr, Ti, Cu, Zn, Ag, and Si, bound with oxygen (O). These materials, which are well-known for their biocompatibility, corrosion resistance, and remarkable mechanical strength, are notable for their adaptability in a variety of settings, demonstrating their robustness and suitability for a broad range of applications. Grain sizes, crystal formations, flaws, and chemical compositions all affect how well oxide ceramics work. Interestingly, these ceramics have molecular structures different from living tissues, are resistant to corrosion and biological organism deterioration, and generally remain stable within the body. Additionally, they can mediate the adhesion and proliferation capabilities of many cell lines, such as mesenchymal stem cells^[75]. Aluminum oxide (Al_2O_3) is the sole oxide that aluminum forms in nature (Alumina, Al_2O_3). Natural forms of aluminum include corundum (Al_2O_3), diaspore ($Al_2O_3 \cdot H_2O$), gibbsite ($Al_2O_3 \cdot 3H_2O$), and bauxite, an impure form of gibbsite. Under normal circumstances, aluminum easily forms a white oxide layer because it is an active amphoteric metal. The most well-known phase changes of Al_2O_3 are α -, β -, and γ - Al_2O_3 ^[75]. Al_2O_3 metal matrix composites' tensile strength rose as the number and size of particles decreased. When compared to other oxide ceramics, composites supplemented with 10 weight percent Al_2O_3 particles show greater tensile strength. Alumina exhibits

exceptional properties, especially in terms of wear resistance and friction, with the most noticeable benefits shown when the grains have a narrow size distribution and are about 4 μm in size^[76]. Infection and other issues pertaining to wound healing have received a lot of attention. Finding novel strategies to manage bacterial infections resistant to antibiotics is crucial for public health. Al_2O_3 NPs show minimal toxicity in eukaryotic animal cells without causing apoptosis. However, research suggests that Al_2O_3 might cause neurotoxicity and oxidative stress, which may result in neuropathologies^[77].

Zirconium oxide (ZrO_2); Zirconia (ZrO_2) exhibits three different polymorphs: cubic, tetragonal, and monoclinic. According to research, a ZrO_2 covering with lateral spacing takes on an ECM-like structure, improving L-929 cell adhesion and proliferation^[77]. Additionally, ZrO_2 -containing composites have demonstrated the ability to stimulate mesenchymal stem cell development^[78]. ZrO_2 has been evaluated for use in wound healing through in-vitro and in-vivo research, as well as randomized clinical trials.

Titanium dioxide (TiO_2): Through nanotechnology research, several TiO_2 nanostructures, such as nanorods, nanotubes, nanowires, and nanobelts, have been created. TiO_2 nanostructures are frequently produced using techniques like hydrothermal, electrochemical, and template-assisted procedures^[79].

Copper oxide (CuO); Cu and CuO NPs' diverse properties make them perfect for a wide range of uses, such as catalyzing the breakdown of organic dyes and performing antimicrobial, catalytic, anticancer, photocatalytic, antiviral, biofilm synthesis, nitrate removal, anti-human pathogen, and photoluminescent activities. Cu is essential for promoting angiogenesis and helping the skin produce and stabilize extracellular matrix (ECM) proteins. The natural repair of skin tissue depends on these processes^[80] used a copper oxide (CuO)-infused wound dressing to treat diabetic mice's wounds. The results showed better blood vessel creation due to increased gene expression and the in-situ presence of proangiogenic factors, including placental growth factor, hypoxia-inducible factor-1 alpha, and vascular endothelial growth factor. Additionally, CuO demonstrates its capacity to immediately aid in the healing of difficult, non-infected wounds on diabetic patients' feet^[81].

Silicon oxide (SiO_2) SiO_2 NPs are synthetic materials that are widely used in many in vitro and in vivo applications. Mesoporous materials have emerged as interesting possibilities for delivering different therapeutic molecules in a regulated and sustainable manner; other polymers, such as PVP, have been combined in with them and cross-linked to form the dressing^[75,82]. Among these, mesoporous SiO_2 NPs are frequently used as delivery agents because of silica's advantageous chemical characteristics, thermal stability, and biocompatibility.

These materials have organized pore configurations that range in size from 2 to 50 nm, resulting in a variety of shaped channels and cavities. Notably, frequent ordered mesoporous frameworks within SiO_2 include the 2D hexagonal planar MCM-41 and SBA-15 structures (symmetry group $p6mm$) with roughly 2 and 10 nm pores, respectively, and the 3D-cubic MCM-48 (symmetric group $la3d$) with roughly 3 nm pores^[83]. *In vitro* toxicology studies have indicated the

tolerability of mesoporous SiO₂ NPs (MSNs) by mice, even at dosages below 100 g/mL. In conventional MSNs, one therapeutic drug dose is loaded per 1 gr of SiO₂, typically ranging from 200 to 300 mg, with a maximum of 600 mg^[84].

Zinc oxide (ZnO) Hexagonal wurtzite and cubic zinc blende are the two main crystal forms of zinc oxide (ZnO). Drug delivery, bioimaging, gene transport, biosensors, and wound healing processes are just a few of the biomedical uses for ZnO that have grown significantly. ZnO NPs are a prospective substitute for antibiotics due to their antibacterial qualities, which make them clever agents against various drug-resistant microorganisms [85]. Additionally, because ZnO effectively reduces inflammation and itching and speeds up the healing process of wounds, it is used in dermatological goods. It is used in dentistry for tooth pastes and temporary fillings. Due to its capability to deliver essential dietary Zn, ZnO is incorporated into various nutritional products and dietary supplements. At the nanoscale, ZnO serves as a UV radiation blocker, catalyst, and biomaterial in the biomedical field, contributing to diagnosis and treatment^[86]. ZnO NPs of larger particle sizes exhibit a high viability rate for fibroblast cells. The antimicrobial activity of ZnO NPs is contingent on particle size, with smaller particles demonstrating enhanced efficacy in combating various microorganisms^[87]

Silver Oxide (Ag₂O); Ag₂O NPs show great promise for treating wounds and provide a practical way to lower the risk of limb amputation. These nanoparticles are the best option for wound dressings because of their exceptional qualities, which include strong antibacterial activity, an efficient anti-inflammatory response, and non-toxic qualities. This ensures safe and successful applications in wound care^[88].

4.2. Silicate-based ceramics silicate

Biodegradable silicate-based bioceramics have recently attracted more attention, particularly in the fields of bone tissue engineering and wound healing. The addition of ions such as Ca, Mg, and Si to silicate bioceramics is known to have a major effect on angiogenesis, cell proliferation, differentiation, and growth, as well as the reduction of inflammatory responses, antibacterial efficacy, and support for re-epithelialization under physiological conditions at the wound site^[89-90]. Akermanite (Ca₂MgSi₂O₇), Diopside (CaMgSi₂O₆), Calcium sodium silicate (Na₂CaSiO₄), Wollastonite (CaSiO₃), Zeolites (M_{2/n}OAl₂O₃·γSiO₂·wH₂O), Bredigite (Ca₇MgSi₄O₁₆), and Hardystonite (Ca₂ZnSi₂O₇) are examples of silicate-based bioceramics that have been used for wound healing.

A recent study^[91] proposed that despite akermanite's widespread use as a calcium silicate-based ceramic in bone regeneration, it exhibits potential applications in wound healing either independently or as part of a composite material. Furthermore, akermanite powder impact on wound healing was explored *in vivo*. Remarkably, wounds treated with akermanite powder exhibited complete healing after 14 days compared to the control group. Akermanite promoted

re-epithelialization by triggering the Wnt/ β -catenin pathway, thereby enhancing the migration and stemness of epidermal cells at the wound site.

The antibacterial qualities of calcium silicates in wound dressings must therefore be taken into account. In one study, the antibacterial activity of diopside, akermanite, and merwinite bioceramics was compared at different concentration levels (500 $\mu\text{g}/100 \mu\text{L}$, 750 $\mu\text{g}/100 \mu\text{L}$, and 1 mg/100 μL) against model bacteria such as *Staphylococcus epidermidis*, *S. aureus*, *E. coli*, and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, even at lower concentrations (500 $\mu\text{g}/100 \mu\text{L}$). Overall, the antibacterial properties of silicate ceramics are attributed to the elevated aqueous pH resulting from the exchange of Ca^{2+} ions with protons from the aqueous medium.

Using calcium silicate ($\text{Na}_2\text{CaSiO}_4$) successfully improved the survival, growth, proliferation, and migration of fibroblasts produced by high glucose, according to another study^[93]. Consequently, this promoted the healing of diabetic lesions and tissue regeneration. By reducing the production of ROS, which are known to contribute to cellular aging in diabetes, the silicon ions recovered from calcium silicate also mitigated fibroblast senescence brought on by elevated glucose. Higher Smad2 phosphorylation, which was followed by increased fibroblast differentiation into myofibroblasts and decreased expression of cellular senescence markers like p53, p16, and p21, were possible causes for the enhanced fibroblast activities. Furthermore, it was found that the in-vivo experiment on diabetic mice increased myofibroblast differentiation and collagen deposition.

In a different study^[94], manganese-doped calcium silicate nanowires were used to create hydrogels using calcium silicates as bioactive components and in situ cross-linking agents. A network structure gel can be created when metal ions, such as Mn^{2+} , chelate with a sodium alginate solution. Nevertheless, the creation of homogeneous hydrogels is hampered by the quick reaction rate. Because manganese doping into calcium silicate nanowires limits manganese release during gelation, the presence of Ca^{2+} ions in calcium silicates permits Mn^{2+} to fill silicate voids or replace Ca^{2+} , leading to a greater release of Ca^{2+} than Mn^{2+} during gelation. Furthermore, tests carried out in vivo and in vitro showed how Si and Mn ions work together to enhance the healing of wounds.

After 15 days, histological results showed that hydrogels made of calcium silicate nanowires doped with manganese promoted quicker healing in diabetic mice, with higher densities of blood vessels, hair follicles, glands, and other skin appendages than calcium alginate and calcium silicate alginate.

Table 3

Overview of selected studies exploring the application of silicate-based ceramics in wound healing.

Bioceramic System	Bioceramic type	Description	Result	Ref
Silicate-based bioceramics	Akermanite	Investigation the effects of Akermanite extract on wound healing.	Akermanite triggered the Wnt/ β -catenin signaling pathway in epidermal cells and increased the expression of epidermal stem cell markers such integrin β 1, Lgr4, Lgr5, and Lgr6.	95
	Calcium silicate	Calcium silicate-stimulated adiposederived stem cells (ADSCs)	Calcium silicate increased ADSC proliferation, increased CXCR4 expression from ADSCs, promoted migration, decreased oxidative stress in ADSCs, and increased the angiogenic potential and migration of human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVEC).	96
	Hardys Zeolite	PLA-hardystonite Janus membrane were prepared. PCL-hardystonite nanofibers were prepared	In addition to excellent exudate absorption, hair follicle regeneration and wound healing were promoted due to the ability to release Zn^{2+} and SiO_3^{-} ions Excellent <i>in vitro</i> cell proliferation and adhesion occurred on the nanofibers and <i>in vivo</i> wound healing was occurred in 21 days.	97 98
	Zn doped wollastonite	Effect of Zn doped wollastonite	The produced nanoparticles had sufficient antibacterial activity against both gram positive and gram negative	99

		nanoparticles on wound healing was evaluated <i>in vitro</i>	bacteria, and they also promoted the adherence and proliferation of fibroblast cells (NIH3T3).	
	Zeolite	Starch-based nanocomposite hydrogel scaffolds reinforced by zeolite nanoparticles	The inclusion of zeolite increased the transparency of scaffolds; induced antibacterial and antioxidant properties; increased epithelialization, collagen formation, angiogenesis, and inflammation reduction	100
		chitosan/zeolite composite films	Zeolites induced ion exchange capacity; reduced water vapor permeation	101
		chitosan/zeolite composite films	The utilization of zeolite showed to augment the quantity of nitric oxide storage while diminishing the rate of gas release	102
		Polylactic acid fibers loaded with nitric oxide (NO)-zeolite	When zeolites were added to the gelatin matrix, the glass transition temperature (37 °C) and dynamic compression modulus (about 737 kPa) increased significantly, and the biodegradation rate and water uptake were regulated in comparison to the control.	103
		Gelatin/zeolite porous scaffold		

4.3. Calcium-phosphates

Calcium-phosphates are a class of biocompatible and bioactive compounds that have been extensively studied for possible application in bone tissue engineering. Because of their superior osteoconductive qualities, these materials can promote bone tissue growth and regeneration. Calcium phosphates have demonstrated promise as wound dressings in addition to their application in bone regeneration^[104,105]. Because of their special ability to promote angiogenesis, elicit immunogenic responses, and address bacterial infections—which are primarily caused by the release of various therapeutic ions—Bio-glasses (BG), a type of calcium phosphate bioceramic, have been primarily used in wound healing, especially in the form of BG particle-

reinforced polymer fibers ^[106]. Two commercial BG fibrous dressing products on the market are Mersilk® and Mirragen® ^[107].

The evaluation of borate bioactive glass micro-fibers (bBG MFs) versus 45S5 Bioglass® (SiG) micro-fibers in thorough comparison research ^[108] showed a clear superiority in the in-vitro bioactivity of the bBG micro-fibers. The outcomes demonstrated a notable enhancement in bioactive response, highlighting the potential of bBG MFs for cutting-edge uses in tissue engineering and biomaterials. bBG micro-fibers are interesting candidates for novel biomedical applications because of their superior in-vitro bioactivity, which is indicative of their improved capacity to stimulate cellular contact, mineralization, and overall biofunctional performance. It was suggested that the presence of a HA layer is what draws in the cells necessary for wound healing. It was shown that BG microfibers showed a greater rate of apatite production than SiG microfibers during a 14-day immersion in PBS. Furthermore, the increased Zeta-potential resulting from HA production has the potential to enhance the absorption of collagen, fibrin, and fibronectin, which effectively stabilizes the wound.

Fig. 6. A schematic illustration outlining the contribution of various ions (both doped and non-doped) released from bioactive glasses at different stages of wound healing.

The potential application of alginate, a biocompatible substance that may gel with Ca^{2+} , in wound dressings has been thoroughly studied ^[109]. A hydrogel made of alginate and chitosan that was enhanced with Zn-doped bioactive glass (Gel-ZBG) was created especially for the purpose of skin wound repair in SD rats in a study ^[110]. By utilizing the synergistic qualities of alginate, chitosan, and Gel-ZBG, this novel hydrogel seeks to offer a cutting-edge solution for efficient wound healing. In-vivo studies conducted after 12 days of therapy showed that Gel-ZBG had

better anti-inflammatory qualities and outperformed Gel (the control sample) in terms of wound closure at the treatment site. Additionally, after six days, the Gel-ZBG-EGF group displayed more fibroblasts and fresh granulation tissue than the control sample. These findings suggest that the system provides Si^{4+} and Ca^{2+} ions, which stimulate the secretion of advantageous factors for angiogenesis by fibroblasts and facilitate wound closure. Fig. 6 illustrates the role of different ions released from bioactive glasses in various stages of wound healing.

Delivering antimicrobial medicines to prevent infections is an essential part of wound healing. Calcium phosphate coatings and wound dressings have been investigated for local antibiotic administration. The use of HA as a carrier is hampered by its low drug affinity, which causes an initial burst release upon administration, despite the material's advantageous characteristics, including biocompatibility, appropriate adsorption capacity, excellent osteoconductivity, bioactivity, high surface area, and desirable mechanical strength. In one investigation, chitosan, gelatin, and polyelectrolyte complex nanofibers were used to encapsulate nano-HA loaded with tetracycline. The elastic modulus rose to 106 MPa in the presence of nano-HA, which is similar to the elastic modulus of human skin (15–80 MPa), according to the results. Furthermore, the dual physical barriers increased the antibacterial therapeutic efficacy by lowering the medication release rate. Additionally, the addition of nano-HA to PEC nanofibers improved their hydration and thermotropic properties, making them ideal for long-term wound care applications. Because of these enhanced qualities, PEC nanofibers are a great option for long-term wound protection^[11].

Table 4

Overview of selected studies exploring the application of calcium-phosphate ceramics in wound healing.

Bioceramic System	Bioceramic type	Description	Result	Ref
Calcium-phosphates	Bioglass	Electrospun chitosan/PVA /bioglass nanofibrous membrane	membranes showed to be effective in healing diabetics; significant increase in the expression of VEGF and TGF- β good spreading and thus stimulating angiogenesis and tissue generation bioglass samples enhanced the	112

		borate based bioglass micro-fibers	formation of blood vessel, showed non-toxicity against human umbilical vein endothelial cells (HUVECs) and the <i>in vivo</i> good reconstruction ability	108
		cerium-doped phosphate glass fibers	the antibacterial activity and controlled release of the ions is improved with doped cerium, and also sample allowed the proliferation of human epidermal keratinocyte (HaCaT) cells and the migration of mice embryonic fibroblasts (MEF); high water uptake (up to 800 %) with improved in mechanical properties in comparison to phosphate glass fibers without cerium	113
		Bioglass activated fibroblast sheet was prepared for wound treatment	By using the prepared construct, blood vessel formation, collagen I synthesis, differentiation of fibroblasts into myofibroblasts and wound healing were facilitated and promoted.	114
	Hydroxyapatite	hydroxyapatite (HA)-containing alginate–gelatin films	The incorporation of HA caused the thermal stability of films; led to a rougher surface; decreased the release rate of tetracycline hydrochloride	115
	Whitlockite	Injectable nanowhitlockite incorporated chitosan hydrogel was prepared for effective hemostasis	Rapid blood clot formation and bleeding control was occurred on rat liver and femoral artery injuries model.	116

Table 5

Overall comparison of different bioceramics in terms of effect on wound healing.

Bioceramic type	Common main effective features
Oxide ceramics	- Antibacterial, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity
Calcium-phosphates	- Angiogenesis stimulation, hemostatic activity, cell stimulation
Silicate-based ceramics	- Antibacterial, antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activity - Stimulation of cell proliferation, angiogenesis and collagen synthesis

Table 5 gives a broad evaluation of how well various bioceramics work in treating wounds based on the aforementioned research. Oxide ceramics usually only emit one kind of inorganic ion, and their antibacterial and anti-inflammatory qualities are frequently used to describe their effects. More inorganic ions are released by calcium-phosphate ceramics, and these bioceramics can be doped with some useful ions. In general, silicate-based ceramics appear to perform and have the most impact on wound healing because of the range of effective releasing ions. As a result, they can be introduced as more ideal bioceramics for wound healing.

Conclusion

Chronic wounds that don't heal are a major worldwide issue that puts a significant financial and social strain on healthcare systems. Numerous research have investigated various materials for the treatment of wounds. Because polymer-based dressings are accessible and reasonably priced, they

are utilized extensively. development factors are costly and decompose rapidly, yet they can aid in the healing of wounds by promoting cell development. Antibiotics and conventional medications may have adverse effects and increase antibiotic resistance.

Because of their powerful mechanical qualities, bioceramics are typically used for bone regeneration, but they also have a lot of potential for wound healing. They are an affordable choice for skin restoration since they can release beneficial inorganic ions. The three primary categories of nanobioceramics utilized in wound treatment—oxide ceramics, silicate-based ceramics, and calcium-phosphate ceramics—are the subject of this review.

The antibacterial and anti-inflammatory properties of oxide ceramics are their primary uses. Beneficial ions can be added to calcium-phosphate ceramics to enhance their ability to halt bleeding and encourage the development of new blood vessels. Because silicate-based ceramics produce a greater variety of ions, they can perform a variety of tasks, including preventing infection, lowering inflammation, promoting the formation of blood vessels, and increasing cell activity. Silicate-based ceramics are therefore thought to be the most promising choice for wound healing.

The primary obstacles to the use of bioceramics are their large-scale and efficient production. High-quality synthesis techniques can be expensive, yet they are still less expensive than making growth factors or medications. To fully comprehend how elements like particle size, shape, dosage, and treatment duration impact healing, more research is required. Additionally, there aren't many clinical investigations, which reduces the reliability of the existing findings.

Future progress may come from new fabrication methods such as microfluidics, polymer-bioceramic composite dressings, nanofibers, 3D-printed scaffolds, and microneedles containing bioceramics. With thorough laboratory, animal, and clinical studies, these approaches could lead to more effective, affordable, and advanced wound-healing treatments.

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